

STRYCHNINE AND BRUCINE. PART IV. A NOTE ON ISOSTRYCHNIC ACID.

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*iso*Strychnic acid is monobasic, gives crystalline salts and undergoes cyclisation with benzoyl chloride and acetic anhydride and with the latter gives *O*-acetyl derivative. With 50% nitric acid it gives dinitro-*iso*strychnic acid and an amorphous acid.

Perkin and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2396) reported that *iso*strychnic acid could neither be benzoylated nor reduced with hydrogen and palladium, while Ciusa described a benzoyl derivative (*Gazzetta*, 1928, 58, 774). The acid after purification and crystallisation (*vide* experimental) had m.p. 240° and on treatment with acetic anhydride gave *O* acetyl*iso*strychnine, m.p. 195-96° (m.p. 133-34°; *O*-acetyldihydrostrychnine, m.p. 195-96°, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2389; Ciusa, *Atti. R. Acad. Lincei*, 1919, 28, 185) while after treatment with benzoyl chloride only *iso*strychnine could be isolated. The acid could not be nitrated with 5% and 10% hot nitric acid but 20% nitric acid gave an amorphous powder (Tafel, *Annalen*, 1898, 301, 285) and with 50% nitric acid crystalline dinitro*iso*strychnic acid nitrate and a second amorphous acid, agreeing with the formula $C_{21}H_{24}O_9N_4 \cdot 3\frac{1}{2}H_2O$, was isolated. *iso*Strychnic acid as well as its acetyl and dinitro derivatives give crystalline salts.

*iso*Strychnic acid as well as *iso*strychnine was accommodated in the formulae of strychnine by Perkin, Robinson and others (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 3051; *Gazzetta*, 1924, 54, 516). The modifications of the strychnine formula have to take cognisance of this substance. The acid, like strychnic acid, is an iminocarboxylic acid and behaves as a monoacid base. Perkin and Robinson pointed out that the acid contains a molecule of water which is probably constitutionally bound, but it is shown in this paper that it is water of crystallisation as half of it is lost at 135° in *vacuo*. Strychnine and its derivatives are known to part with solvent of crystallisation with great difficulty. The acid shows the presence of a hydroxyl group in the molecule as evidenced by its acetylation and its cyclisation to *iso*strychnine with acetic anhydride. The alcoholic hydroxyl is postulated to be formed by scission of the oxide ring of strychnine and the carboxyl group by the rupture of the cyclic amide group under the influence of basic catalysts such as barium hydroxide and sodium ethoxide. The reaction is not fully understood.

but it is certain that the ether oxygen atom and the $N\cdot CO\cdot CH_2\cdot$ group are involved. The formation of an acetyl derivative, the existence of a carboxyl group together with the fact that *isostrychnine* and its derivatives do not give isonitroso or benzylidene derivatives support the view. *iso*-Strychnine has a double bond and on reduction gives dihydro*iso*strychnine, distinct from dihydrostrychnine, and thus the isomerism of the two is independent of double bond. Besides these some other changes also take place in the molecule. Pictet and Bacovescu have shown that a sulphonic acid of *iso*strychnine could not be isolated and that the molecule is readily oxidised by potassium permanganate. Similar discrepancy is observed in the present investigation as dinitro*iso*strychnic acid can not be reduced, while the corresponding dinitrostrychnic acid under identical conditions gives diaminostrychnine.

It is probable that under the influence of basic catalysts a number of deep-seated changes takes place in the strychnine molecule and an extensive study of the subject is necessary to solve the problem.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

*iso*Strychnic Acid, its Salts and Derivatives.

*iso*Strychnic acid was prepared by heating strychnine with barium hydroxide and water in an autoclave and was isolated in clusters of prisms. The impure crystalline acid was dissolved in the least quantity of dilute sodium hydroxide solution, and after adding sufficient alcohol and ether to keep the whole into solution, the dark impurities which separated were removed. From the light orange solution, amorphous cream-coloured *iso*strychnic acid was precipitated with acetic acid, well washed with water and alcohol and then crystallised from methyl alcoholic acetic acid in snow-white small prisms, m.p. 240° (decomp.) (Perkin and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2396, give m.p. 231°). Its solution in concentrated sulphuric acid with a little potassium dichromate gave greenish yellow colour which finally turned green but with 60% sulphuric acid an orange-red solution was obtained; with a crystal of potassium chlorate in concentrated sulphuric acid it turned red and in concentrated and dilute hydrochloric acid with a little potassium dichromate, a red solution was obtained which soon turned into deep blood or cherry colour. It crystallised with one mol. of water, half of which was lost at 135° . (Found: loss, 1.8. $\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires 2.5 per cent). (Found in material dried at 135° in *vacuo*: C, 70.0; H, 7.6; N, 8.1. $C_{21}H_{24}O_2N_2$, $\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires C, 69.8; H, 7.8; N, 7.8 per cent).

The *hydrochloride*, precipitated by adding ether to a clear solution of the acid in a few drops of methyl alcoholic hydrochloric acid, was crystallised from alcohol-ether mixture in needles, m.p. 190-95° (frothing). (Found in material dried at 110°: Cl, 8'5. $C_{21}H_{24}O_3N_2$, H_2O , HCl requires Cl, 8'7 per cent).

The *picrate* was prepared in acetone solution. The residue after removal of acetone was well washed with acetone-ether mixture and crystallised from methyl alcohol in pale yellow prisms, m.p. 187-89° (decomp. 130°).

Action of Acetic Anhydride on isoStrychnic Acid: Acetylisostrychnine.—*isoStrychnic acid* (2 g.) was heated with acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) at 100° for 5 minutes, when the acid dissolved to a red solution which after dilution with water (50 c.c.) was further heated for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The filtered solution after cooling was made alkaline with ammonia and was extracted with chloroform. The residue from the dry chloroform extract was crystallised from alcohol-chloroform in prisms, m.p. 195-96° (decomp.). The substance is sparingly soluble in alcohol. A solution of the base in concentrated sulphuric acid with a little potassium dichromate turned light violet and finally on long keeping brown, but if the solution was diluted with water the violet colour turned into golden yellow. The sulphuric acid solution of the base with a trace of potassium chlorate turned light greenish yellow which on dilution and keeping developed a light pink tinge, while the base in concentrated hydrochloric acid produced a golden yellow colour. At 100° in *vacuo* it lost 2 mols. H_2O (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 69'3; H, 6'9; N, 6'9; $COCH_3$, 9'8. $C_{21}H_{22}O_2N_2 \cdot COCH_3$, H_2O requires C, 69'8; H, 6'8; N, 7'1; $COCH_3$, 10'9 per cent).

The *hydrochloride* was obtained as a microcrystalline powder by adding dry hydrogen chloride in ether to a chloroform solution of the base. After reprecipitation with ether from methyl alcoholic solution it had m.p. 225-26°. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: Cl, 8'2. $C_{23}H_{27}O_4N_2$, HCl requires Cl, 8'2 per cent).

The *picrate* was obtained by adding ether solution of picric acid to a chloroform solution of the base and is soluble in alcohol and water, m.p. 184° (decomp.).

Action of Benzoyl Chloride on isoStrychnic Acid: Formation of isoStrychnine.—*isoStrychnic acid* (2 g.) was suspended in dry pyridine and benzoyl chloride (0'9 g.) was added in the ice-cold; the substance dissolved on shaking and the resultant red solution on standing overnight deposited a crystalline hydrochloride, which was well washed with ether and dried in *vacuo* over phosphorus pentoxide. The ether solution furnished benzoic

acid. The hydrochloride was recrystallised from methyl alcohol but only 1·2 g. could be obtained and no definite product could be isolated from the mother-liquors. The crystalline hydrochloride was dissolved in chloroform, made alkaline with a drop of alcoholic potassium hydroxide and the solution dried over sodium sulphate. The straw-coloured solution on keeping deposited prisms which after washing with a little water and alcohol had m.p. 219-20° (decomp.). It gave the same colour reactions as *isostrychnic acid*. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 68·0; H, 7·2; N, 7·4. $C_{21}H_{22}O_2N_2, 2H_2O$ requires C, 68·10; H, 7·00; N, 7·57 per cent). Obviously it was *isostrychnine* (*cf. J. Chem. Soc., 1927, 2389*, where m.p. 220° is recorded).

Action of Nitric Acid on isoStrychnic Acid.—Nitration was tried with 5% and 10% nitric acid by refluxing the acid for several hours but no definite substance could be isolated. Nitric acid (20%) gave an amorphous dinitro-*iso*-acid (*cf. Tafel, loc. cit.*), but on raising the concentration to 50% well defined products were obtained. *isoStrychnic acid* (5 g.) was dissolved in 50% nitric acid in a glass dish and heated on the boiling water-bath with constant stirring when the solution turned deep red and finally faded to a deep orange-yellow colour with simultaneous evolution of nitrous fumes and separation of a dull yellow crystalline powder in prisms (A, 3 g.). The whole process took about 5-7 minutes. The filtrate on dilution with water gave an amorphous brown-red precipitate (B, 0·8 g.).

Fraction B.—The amorphous acid charred from 260-70° and was soluble in methanol, dissolved sparingly in ethanol and readily in acetone. It was also soluble in ammonia, alkalis and in acetic acid from which it came down on dilution with water. The acid could not be induced to crystallise and gave the following analytical data after drying at 100° in *vacuo*. (Found: C, 46·8; H, 6·0; N, 10·1 per cent).

Fraction A: Dinitroisostrychnic Acid.—This mass was obtained in aggregates of prisms when the hydrochloric acid solution of "A" was filtered into dilute ammonia containing a little alcohol. It was washed with water and alcohol. It is insoluble in alcohol, water and other common organic solvents and it does not melt below 325°. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 53·43; H, 5·3; N, 11·6. $C_{21}H_{22}O_7N_4, 1\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires C, 53·7; H, 5·3; N, 12·0 per cent). The acid like dinitrostrychnic acid is basic in character and forms well defined crystalline salts which do not melt below 325°.

The *hydrochloride*, sparingly soluble in alcohol, was obtained in aggregates of needles when the acid was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid or methyl alcoholic hydrochloric acid.

The *sulphate* was obtained in long needles on addition of methyl alcohol to a sulphuric acid solution of dinitroisostrychnic acid nitrate.

Action of Reducing Agents on Dinitroisostrychnic Acid.—Dinitroisostrychnic acid (1·8 g.), concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.), and zinc (2 g.) were warmed on the boiling water-bath when the deep red solution turned greenish, bluish and finally slightly red in colour. The filtered solution on cooling was made ammoniacal with concentrated ammonia, zinc removed with hydrogen sulphide but nothing definite could be isolated from the dark filtrate.

Stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid and methyl alcoholic hydrochloric acid and iron did not give any definite reduction products.

The micro-analyses were done by Drs. Weiller and Strauss of Oxford. The author wishes to express his sincere thanks to Professor Sir Robert Robinson, Kt., F.R.S., for his advice and encouragement throughout this investigation and to the Trustees, Dawoodbhoy Fazalbhoy Muslim Educational Trust, Bombay, for an Educational loan which enabled the author to take part in this investigation.

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Received November 24, 1935.
